

GENDER RELATIONS IN MUSIC INSTRUMENT ORIENTATION AND PERFORMANCE: BALANCING THE EQUATION

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Abstract

In music instrumental performance, right from the orientation, there is an unequal relationship between the male and female gender. For example, in the choice of instruments, especially for educational purposes, some instruments are estimated as masculine while others are merely feminine. In this context, learners and would-be players are exposed to a contested site and imbalance in the equation of musical creativity and performativity. Are there gender relations in musicality or performativity? This article explores how the anomaly (imbalance in musical creativity and performativity) has been challenged in recent trajectories in the Department of Music, University of Uyo, Nigeria. The study examines three examples of how three female performers, against all odds, have negotiated male-dominated musical instruments; thus, balancing the gender equation. Through unstructured oral interviews, participant observations, and theorizing, the study discusses the need to balance the gender equation in musical instrument performances. The advocacy towards balancing the equation is motivated by multifaceted inequalities of gender relations in the Nigerian society.

Keywords: Gender, Music Instruments, Performance Orientation, Inequality, Balance.

Introduction

In the Ibibio society of Nigeria, as in many traditional societies of Africa, when a child is born, the first question is what is the gender? girl or boy? The reaction becomes contested or is received with mixed feelings depending on what the parents wanted, that is, if they had a child or children and wanted more to balance the gender equation in their family, or, merely first-time parents. The recurrence of this scenario in our modern society is very disturbing, but to envisage its prototype with gender relations to musical creativity or performativity is to imagine the absurd. Generally, everybody is musical, and

the musicality of a child is tested at birth with the first cry. The intensity (example amplitude) of the child's first cry is heard as the loudness or softness of the variation of cry pitches and can be measured in units called decibels. Importantly, the amount of energy demonstrated in the baby's cry portends the inevitable physiological and psychological arousal to the mother. The intensity also may ignite the joy of heralding another singer for a musical family. However, there is always the need to balance the gender equation in such families. That is, soprano and alto for the female vocal parts, and tenor and bass for the male texture. Significantly, the vocal range such as bass comes with maturity, which means that no child is born with the vocal texture of the male range. The implication is that both male and female children sing at the approximate range for soprano and alto vocal parts, a balanced gender equation that is often underestimated.

However, in musical instrument performance, there seems to be a different orientation, which superimposes an unequal relationship between the male and female gender. For example, in the choice of instruments, especially for educational purposes, some instruments are estimated to be exclusively masculine while others are merely feminine. In this context, learners and would-be players are exposed to a contested site, an imbalance in the equation of musical creativity and performativity. Are there gender relations in musicality or performativity? To answer this question, This work looked into musical instrument performance because as noted in the introductory remarks, singing creates a reasonable model of gender balance than it is found in musical instrument performance. This article explores how the music instrument anomaly (example, imbalance in music creativity and performativity) has been challenged in recent trajectories in the Department of Music, University of Uyo, Nigeria. The study examined three examples of how three female performers, against all odds, have negotiated male-dominated musical instruments; thus, balancing the gender equation. Through unstructured oral interviews, participant observations, and theorizing, the study discusses the need to balance the gender equation in musical instrument performances. The advocacy towards balancing the equation is motivated by multifaceted inequalities in the Nigerian society, and specifically, towards the expansion of models of African feminism to include samples in musical performances.

From Feminism to African Feminism

The term 'feminism' as a theory has been highly contentious and controversial. In other words, the central problem with discourses on feminism has been the inability to either arrive at a consensus of opinion about what feminism is, or how to accept definitions that could serve as a point of unification. Similarly, despite these challenges, the adoption of the term feminism in African feminism signifies the role that African women play in the "... fight for equal opportunities and access to health, economic and educational resources and decision-making positions in both private and public domains" (Atanga 2013). In this context, this article accepts narrowly with African feminism for its equality tenors that resonate with balancing gender equality in music instrument performance.

Male Dominance in Music Instrument Performance

Interestingly, when deciding on an instrument to study, there is always a notion regarding what was considered appropriate for women to play since some instruments are masculine and others are feminine. The argument in this gendering of musical instruments is that male students are often free to pick any instrument despite gender relations. Notably, the large majority of instrumentalists are male when looking at the older generation of musicians in striking contrast to the female minority in the younger generation. In addition, the Nigerian music industry is male-dominated not because of any restriction but interest. This is not so for traditional music, there are different restrictions and taboos associated with the female gender and instrumentation, but the question has always been: What does gender have to do with music? (Werner 2019). Several debates have shown that music is in itself "a dynamic mode of gender" "an essentially gendered discourse", "a marker of sexual identity..." and is meaningful only within a context of "... gender, race and ethnicity" (Sergeant and Himonides 2016). In other words, musical meaning is dependent on social and cultural context, and it is 'socially and culturally constructed' since music is a culturally defined artifact. The implication is that in many cultures of the world, gender roles are designated to children as soon as there are born according to the *gender ideology* of that society.

The term *gender ideology* has been used to denote the conceptual and valuative framework that underlies and structures appropriate behaviors for women and men (Koskoff, 2014). Furthermore, the author explained that gender ideologies are most often codified as religious, moral, or legal systems

that justify relations between the genders. For example, for many centuries, the traditional belief in male supremacy found in many Western religious systems (Christianity, Judaism, Islam) promoted the idea that women were not suited for religious leadership. Indeed, written texts supported and validated this ideology, and it is only recently that such beliefs have been questioned by both men and women.

There is changing trajectory in the European patriarchal gender ideologies and imperialism. “During the past two decades, sweeping changes in women's economic and political status have resulted in many new opportunities for women within the historically male-dominated Western classical music tradition” (Koskoff, 2014).

turn to musical instruments.

Musical Instruments as a Codified Source of Power

Musical instruments are significant cultural artefacts invested with a wide range of meanings and powers. Through their presence and through the sounds music has a special ability to transform consciousness. All around the world, instrumental sounds are indispensable to many religious and secular rituals, and in some situations, instruments achieve iconic status (Doubleday, 2008). In Nigeria, among the Ibibios, the gender relations between men and women are characterised by strict restrictions on women. Udoh (2018) opined that “Some of the informants/aged men and women contacted explained that those supposed restrictions were necessary regarding the metaphysical belief systems around the making and functions of some of these instruments” such as *Ikon*, *Ibid*, *Obodom*, and *Uta*. Udo (2018) further explained that, some restrictions were protective of women while others had a metaphorical significance that showed the superiority of women in power relations. For ritual instruments, it was observed that allowing women on their menstrual cycle to touch or play the drums will render the ritualistic power impotent.

In many instances, gender relations in instrumental performance were a relationship set up between the instrument and performer, creating a contested site of meaning. Furthermore, as objects whose sounds have transformative power, musical instruments are frequently endowed with personhood, of masculinity or femininity. It is common to find men with the trumpet and women with the violin, in Western art music, and men play the instruments while women dance and sing in traditional settings. The argument here is that gendered meanings, no matter how engrained in the societies, are part of an

instrument's personhood, and as such they are fluid and negotiable. For instance, certain notions that females tend to be less likely to have a forced, brassy sound, but that women seem to have a nicer/darker sound are nebulous. Ostensibly, musical expressivities have nothing to do with gender, but the natural ability to play in response to good musicianship and musical expressions according to the level of work the performer puts into his/her rehearsal. Quality tones vary from person to person and have nothing to do with gender. From the foregoing, the aspect of musicality or performativity contrast between males and females in the selected instruments (*Ikon Eto -Xylophone*, Trumpet, and Drum set) and players are relatively made clearer as it is obvious that the major factor is musical orientation.

Gender Relations in Musical Orientation

In most cultures of the world, “musical roles are divided along gender lines: women sing and men play. Of course, men also sing, and women sometimes play; yet, unlike men, women who play often do so in contexts of sexual and social marginality” (Koskoff 2014). In commercial music, the need for the expression of equality in musical performances is guided by the historical oppression of women or simply, the dominance of men over women in the public spheres, particularly in instrumental performance. But the most important issue here is that the girl child should be told she has the right to play any instrument of her choice. This must become the new musical orientation. Thus, African feminism moves beyond a platform of political redress which has as its goal the achievement of equal opportunity for women with men, into its fundamental task of examining how women have been represented in diverse activities in our society to stem all forms of subordination to women (Hamer 2021). Indeed, the past twenty years have witnessed the documentation of the roles women have played as composers, performers, patrons, impresarios, and critics. This has been necessary because of the twisted orientation and relationship between art, gender, and power. Historically, debates on African feminism of the last twenty years have sought to unmask gender roles and political ideology embedded in literature, art, and film, towards an ideology that has served to privilege the masculine over the feminine, which has severely constrained women's creative opportunities (Kouvaras, et al., 2022).

Concluding Remarks

Gender meanings and relationships may be applied to any artifact, therefore to any musical instrument; such an orientation should be eschewed in musical creativity and performativity. Gender relations and sex role differentiation were constructed in different societies by different standards according to certain beliefs of the past. For example, through a ritual enactment of *Ekpo* music among the Ibibio, *Ekpo* cult members created a style of hegemonic masculinity, setting a dominant standard against which other masculinities are defined, so uninitiated men are also rigorously excluded. However, in modern terms, such demeaning structures should be jettisoned or their balancing mechanisms be sorted to create a more friendly and all-inclusive society.

In conclusion, musical creativity and performativity in musical instruments are merely symbolic gestures, which depend on individual abilities and the potential to externalise emotional, physical, and social creative energies.

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